

Resistive Self-Sensing Controllable Fabric-Based Actuator: A Novel Approach to Creating Anisotropy

Ayşe Feyza Yılmaz, Kadir Özlem, Fidan Khalilbayli, Mehmet Fatih Celebi, Fatma Kalaoglu, Asli Tuncay Atalay, Gökhan Ince, and Ozgur Atalay*

Designing advanced soft robots with soft sensing capabilities for real-world applications remains challenging due to the intricate integration of actuation and sensor capabilities, which require diverse materials and complex procedures. This paper introduces a fabric-based robotic technology featuring an “all textile-based self-sensing pneumatic actuator” and a low-cost resistive strain sensor created through simple sewing techniques. The novel approach eliminates the need for additional strain-limiting woven fabric, simplifying the manufacturing process. It also enables the development of bioinspired motions such as bending, twisting, and snake-like movements. The electromechanical behaviors of the sensor and bending actuator are tested for their performance under positive air pressure. Through mathematical modeling, the actuator’s sensing capacity is estimated accurately, providing precise feedback for pressure and position control. Different closed-loop controller types, including On–Off and Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) control, are evaluated for their effectiveness. Furthermore, the practical application of the sensing actuator is demonstrated by integrating it into a wearable glove, showcasing its enhanced sensing capabilities for finger-like soft wearable robotic applications. This research tackles the challenges associated with designing advanced soft robots with integrated sensing capabilities, offering a promising fabric-based solution that can drive significant advancements in real-world applications.

worms, and flowers, through the careful selection and construction of appropriate soft materials.^[1–7] Elastomers,^[8] hydrogels,^[9] shape memory alloys,^[10] and self-healing polymers^[11] have been utilized to create fundamental bioinspired kinematics, encompassing bending,^[12,13] extending,^[14] and twisting motions.^[15,16] The bioinspired kinematics devised for specific application areas are based on the design, mechanical deformation, and straining range capabilities of the chosen materials. Textile materials are highly suitable for constructing soft actuators due to their lightweight, compliant, low-cost, hierarchical structure, and compatibility with the human body.^[17,18] While most research on textile-based actuators has predominantly focused on bending motion,^[19–24] the ability to design various motions for textile-based soft robotics holds the potential to expand the scope of new application scenarios.

Fabric-based bending actuators often entail intricate design elements such as folding, pleating, or the construction of double-layered fabric structures. The

technique of mechanical anisotropy is employed to induce bending motion in these double-layered fabric designs, which consist of two different textile layers, including elastic and strain-limiting fabric.^[19–23] However, this approach has inherent limitations,

1. Introduction

Soft robotics has achieved remarkable progress in emulating various organisms found in nature, including humans, fish,

A. F. Yılmaz, F. Kalaoglu, A. T. Atalay, O. Atalay
 Faculty of Textile Technologies and Design
 Textile Engineering Department
 Istanbul Technical University
 Istanbul 34437, Turkey
 E-mail: atalayoz@itu.edu.tr

K. Ozlem, F. Khalilbayli, G. Ince
 Faculty of Computer and Informatics Engineering
 Computer Engineering Department
 Istanbul Technical University
 34469 Istanbul, Turkey
 M. F. Celebi
 Faculty of Technology
 Mechatronics Engineering Department
 Marmara University
 34854 Istanbul, Turkey

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/adsr.202300108>

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such as the requirement of separate fabric panels for strain limitation and elasticity, susceptibility to failure at weak points during inflation, and the occurrence of shrinkage at the seams, compromising the mechanical properties of engineered structures.

Moreover, various welding technologies have been employed to bond fabric layers in the fabrication of fabric actuators.^[21–24] Nonetheless, these bonding methods exhibit limitations, such as the inability to use non-thermoplastic materials and the challenge of achieving a robust molecular bond in areas where chemically incompatible thermoplastics converge. On the other hand, knitting technology is limited in its availability due to the high initial investment costs and the need for extensive professional expertise in actuator design.

Before textile-based actuators can be effectively utilized in real-world controllable applications, compliant sensing properties must be incorporated into their stretchable structures. Integrating sensors into the design of these actuators provides valuable information about their motion or position.^[25–27] To ensure that the actuation motion is not impeded, the sensors must possess stretchable, adaptive, lightweight, and compliant characteristics, akin to the actuators themselves.

While numerous fabrication techniques exist for producing sensors^[28–33] and actuators^[34–39] separately, it is crucial to focus on the method of sensor integration into the actuator. Coating and printing processes using conductive polymers or pastes, as well as chemical bonding, can be employed to incorporate sensors onto stretchable actuator bodies.^[30] However, these methods are time-consuming and often result in an inhomogeneous distribution of electrically conductive polymers, slippage issues, and poor interfacial adhesion between the sensor structure and actuator. Thus, achieving complete interfacial attachment and material compatibility between the soft actuator and sensing element is of paramount importance for accurately capturing the actuator's true motion and preventing delamination at connection points during actuation.

To overcome the aforementioned challenges, we present, for the first time, a resistive self-sensing fabric-based pneumatic actuator fabricated entirely using low-cost sewing technology. In this paper, we provide comprehensive insights into the design, fabrication, sensing, characterization, and control of this self-sensing actuator. Additionally, utilizing the same fabrication technique, we demonstrate the creation of bioinspired soft robots capable of mono-directional twisting and snake-like movements. Following sensor and actuator characterization, we mathematically model the sensing behavior of the bending actuator to showcase its controllability. Furthermore, we systematically evaluate and compare the performance of ON–OFF and PID closed-loop controllers.

2. Results and Discussion

The actuation structure in textile-based actuators is crucial to controlling and generating motion with textile materials. In previous studies, a two-layered construction consisting of stretch knit fabric and non-stretch, strain-limiting woven fabric has been commonly employed to provide bending motion in textile-based actuators.^[19–23] In contrast, this work aims to eliminate the need for an additional non-stretch woven fabric by introducing a novel approach. Instead, we use stretch knit fabric that is com-

mercially available as the only material for the actuator's body and incorporate strain-limiting capabilities using sewing technology to achieve anisotropy. To demonstrate the feasibility of our anisotropy method, we showcase soft actuators capable of bending like human fingers, twisting like the human body, and mimicking snake-like biomotion (**Figure 1**; Movie S1, Supporting Information). This is made possible by strategically placing stitches on the knit fabrics in individually designed patterns for each specific motion. Rather than relying on woven textiles, we harnessed the flexibility of knit fabric through a stitching technique, slightly reducing its natural stretchiness to a level comparable to woven textiles. This strategy for producing anisotropy highlights the possibilities for adaptable, affordable soft robotic systems and emphasizes the value of programmable stitches for a range of applications.

The primary objective of this research is to develop a self-sensing pneumatic bending actuator that incorporates a stitched-based resistive sensor to enable direct sensor feedback from the actuator's stretching surface for precise control. The high elasticity of the lycra substrate utilized in the actuator provides the stretchable fabric with exceptional strain-sensing capabilities. Before sensor integration, we determine the stretch direction of the knit fabric using a uniaxial tensile machine. The knit fabric is cut using laser cutting in both the course and wale directions, as depicted in **Figure 2a**. The fabric sample exhibits a 100 mm extension at 32 N in the course direction and a 100 mm extension at 90 N in the wale direction, as illustrated in **Figure 2b**.

The actuation performance of textile-based actuators is significantly influenced by factors such as the thickness and knit structure of the fabric. The knit structure plays a crucial role in determining the actuator's stretchability and range of motion. For applications requiring specific movements or deformations, selecting an appropriate knit structure is essential. The choice of knit structure has a profound impact on stretchability and the extent of achievable motion. We used the 1 × 1 rib knit structure, which results in significantly higher strain values in the course direction compared to the wale direction. This is especially important for sensing actuator applications that demand precise and tailored movements. Besides, thicker knit fabrics tend to resist deformations, which is particularly important when aiming for precise and controlled movements. Thicker fabrics require higher pressure levels or airflow rates to achieve specific motions compared to thinner fabrics. The selection of fabric thickness should be a deliberate design choice, tailored to the specific requirements of the application. We found that the 1 × 1 rib knit fabric with a thickness of 0.3 mm is the optimum choice for our application.

In the context of the rib knit structure's loop pattern, the knit fabric demonstrates significantly higher strain values in the course direction compared to the wale direction. Therefore, the integration of the sensor is carried out along the course direction to ensure substantial changes in electrical signals and enable rapid bending deformation even at low air pressure. This strategic placement of the sensor facilitates enhanced sensitivity and responsiveness in capturing the motion of the actuator. By leveraging the remarkable properties of the lycra substrate and carefully aligning the sensor integration along the course direction, our self-sensing pneumatic bending actuator achieves remarkable strain-sensing capabilities.

Figure 1. The novel method provided to create bio-inspired bending, snake-like, and twisting actuators.

The utilization of a zigzag stitch with a high stitch density presents challenges in the fabrication process, including the potential puncturing of the knit fabric due to its flexible and looping nature, as well as the risk of breaking the machine needle. To effectively address these problems, a simple strategy is employed, involving the immersion of the knit fabric in starch to enhance its stiffness, sewing performance, and suitability for high-density zigzag stitching. (Figure 2c). In the construction of the sensor, we employ a conductive thread that offers a range of desirable properties, including lightweightness, softness, durability, and resistance to deformation. Through the application of sewing techniques, the sensor is integrated at the top of the bending actuator, enabling precise sensing capabilities. The sensor is meticulously fabricated using the 304 zigzag stitch geometry, as depicted in Figure 2d. This stitch type is specifically chosen for its remarkable stretchability, allowing unrestricted motion of the actuator and preserving the inherent flexibility of the fabric to the greatest extent possible. By immersing the knitted fabric in a starch solution and utilizing a conductive thread in the fabrication of the sensor, we overcome the challenges associated with the zigzag stitch, ensuring the integrity and longevity of the actuator.

In the construction process, the conductive thread is specifically employed in the bobbin thread region of the sewing machine, while a polyester stitch thread is utilized in the needle thread area. This strategic use of materials ensures optimal performance and functionality. Once the fabrication of the sensor is completed, the fabric undergoes a rinsing process with warm water to remove any residual starch, followed by thorough drying (Figure 2e). By combining the conductive yarn with the knit fabric through stitching, we achieve an inherent stretchability in the sensor. When the flexible and stretchable sensor is subjected to strain from one or two sides, the adjacent conductive threads undergo separation, resulting in a discernible change in resistance (Figure 2e). This mechanism allows for precise sensing capabilities, enabling the actuator to accurately detect and respond to external stimuli. Through the integration of conductive threads and the utilization of stitching techniques, we have successfully developed a versatile and adaptable sensor that enhances the functionality of the fabric-based actuator. The resulting stretchability and the ability to detect resistance changes contribute to the actuator's controllability and responsiveness, further solidifying its potential for a wide range of real-world applications.

We present a straightforward and cost-effective approach for fabricating a sensor-integrated, mechanically bending anisotropy

actuator using sewing technology, as depicted in Figure 2f. By employing 301 lockstitches at four tension settings, we stitch widthwise, longitudinal, and two cross-stitches to impart the desired bending characteristic to the textile fabric.

The actuator's widthwise and longitudinal lines are sewn at regular 0.5 cm intervals, with a width of 2 cm and a length of 13 cm. The longitudinal stitches serve to relieve strain in the knitted fabric, mimicking the properties of the woven fabric used in earlier studies.^[19,40]

Meanwhile, the widthwise lines are sewn together to prevent radial expansion of the actuator. To emulate the joints in a human finger, two cross-stitches are incorporated, effectively enhancing the bending angle of the actuator. Although the human finger possesses three joints – the distal interphalangeal joint (DIP), the proximal interphalangeal joint (PIP), and the metacarpophalangeal joint (MCP)^[41] – we find that three cross-stitches actually reduce the bending angle of the actuator. Thus, our actuator accurately replicates the soft-sewn distal interphalangeal and metacarpophalangeal joints. Furthermore, the inclusion of two cross-stitches significantly enhances the controllability of the sensing actuator's electrical feedback, preventing electrical signals from rapidly saturating.

After completing the stitching of the bending anisotropy threads, the stitched fabric is transformed into a tubular actuator. An airtight thermoplastic polyurethane bladder is inserted into the actuator, and controlled air pressure is applied, as depicted in Figure 2g. In the development of pneumatic actuators, it is crucial to ensure actuation stability and the actuator's ability to maintain its bending shape over an extended period without gas leaks affecting its performance. To address these concerns, we selected a high-quality thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) film (Stretchlon 200, Fiber Glast, Brookville, OH, USA). Additionally, the thermoplastic polyurethane film undergoes thorough cleaning to prevent welding problems caused by dust or dirt. It should be wiped with a non-linting soft cloth or sponge. The welding thickness is set at 0.5 cm to minimize the risk of the welded region suddenly opening under air pressure. To assess the impermeability of the air bladder and detect any adhesion problems, an air leakage test is conducted by immersing the air bladder in water. It's important to note that the successful creation of a high-quality air bladder is indicated by the absence of bubbles when air pressure is applied to the bladder submerged in water. The actuator, consisting of a single continuous piece of knit fabric, has no seams along its sides, as illustrated in Figure 2h. This design ensures structural integrity and optimal performance.

Figure 2. The fabrication process of the stitched-based sensor with electrically conductive yarn and bending textile actuator. a) Laser cutting of the knit fabric. b) Tensile testing of the knit base fabric to determine the strain direction. c) Starching process of the knit fabric to stiffen it. d) Stitching process to fabricate the sensor using a flexible zigzag stitch type on the starched knit fabric. e) Washing and drying of the starched resistive stitched sensor and stretching of the stitched sensor. f) Creation of bending anisotropy utilizing sewing technology, followed by folding and stitching of the corner edges to form a bending textile actuator. g) Insertion of a bladder within the 2D textile bending actuator. h) Demonstration of the inflated sensing textile actuator with no visible seams.

2.1. Electromechanical Characterization

The limited availability of flexible, elastic, compliant, and self-recovering integrated sensors on soft actuators has created significant barriers to the progress of soft robotics. In this study, we present an approach that involves the design of a stitched strain sensor with resistive sensing capabilities. The sensor employs conductive yarn as the sensing element, while the non-

conductive knit fabric imparts elasticity and durability to the system (Movie S2, Supporting Information). When the conductive threads make contact, the electrical length of the structure decreases, resulting in a decrease in resistance. Conversely, when the conductive stitches are separated, the electrical length increases, leading to an increase in resistance. However, accurately predicting how the stitching parameters influence resistance change proves to be a complex task. The yarn, consisting of

Figure 3. Electromechanical characterization of the stitched-based strain sensor and sensing textile actuator. a) Sensitivity of the sensor. b) Electrical response under 60% loading and unloading strain for 2000 cycles, demonstrating the durability and stability of the sensor with low creep. c) Resistivity changes with bending straining. d) Comparison of bending angle-pressure between the non-sensitized and sensitized actuators. e) Bending angle-resistance change-pressure relationship of the sensing actuator. f) Gripping force-pressure relationship of the sensing actuator.

filaments and staple fibers, coupled with the structural design, introduces the possibility of contact or non-contact of the fabric's looped structure during straining. While the conductivity of the electrically conductive yarn exhibits linearity, the introduction of curvature and mechanical stresses during manufacturing may induce non-linear behavior when the yarn is applied to a textile-knitted structure. To gain a comprehensive understanding of the conductive yarn's properties, conductivity measurements are conducted. **Figure 3** provides an in-depth electromechanical characterization of the stitched-based strain sensor and sensing actuator, showcasing their performance and behavior in detail.

When the actuator undergoes its maximum bending deformation, the sensor exhibits an extension of $\approx 60\%$ of the actuation strain. To assess the sensitivity of the sensors, they were subjected to 2000 cycles of testing using a 60% strain level and a 60% cyclical load. Figure 3a illustrates the sensor's relative shift in resistive signal, providing insight into its electrical properties under a 60% mechanical strain. The electrical response sensitivity of the sensor is represented by a fitted function with an R^2 value of 0.98, following a third-order polynomial function that enables calibration through an electrical circuit. The strain sensor demonstrates a gauge factor (GF) of 0.27. The response of the sensor to stretching reveals an increasing resistance change with higher strain levels, accompanied by low hysteresis. Figure 3b displays a loading-unloading graph depicting 2000 cycles at strain levels ranging from 0% to 60%, with minor fluctuations observed in the relative resistance change across the five loading-unloading cycles. Following 2000 cycles of stretching, the variation of R/R_0

remains virtually constant in each cycle. These minor changes could be attributed to stitch readjustment and the sliding of conductive yarn within the knit structure during sensor recovery. The sensor's stability, repeatability, and sensitivity contribute to the accurate detection of actuator bending motion.

Sensor-based closed-loop control plays a crucial role in the field of soft robotics. It involves collecting data through tests conducted on the sensing actuator, followed by modeling.^[42–44] Previous studies have utilized adhesive techniques to integrate rigid sensors, commercially available flexible sensors,^[45] and textile capacitive sensors.^[44] In contrast, our approach involves the complete integration of a stitched strain sensor into the body of the actuator, ensuring reliable data representation of the actuator's dynamics. Our compliant flexible stitched-based sensor, unlike polymer-based sensors, exhibits excellent durability, remaining intact even when subjected to expansion over time. By utilizing a flexible stitch-based resistive sensor, the angular motion of the actuator is accurately measured, with the resistance altering proportionally to the degree of bending. Figure 3c demonstrates the relationship between the sensor's relative resistance change (R/R_0) and the associated bending angle, obtained through position feedback (Movie S3, Supporting Information). The relative resistance varies as the sensor geometry reacts to the actuator's bending, pressure, and strain effects. Notably, during the actuator's 180° bending motion, the sensor's resistance decreases almost linearly. This decrease is attributed to the separation of conductive yarn contact points resulting from the combined effects of strain, bending, and radial expansion. Remarkably, the stitched

Figure 4. Demonstration application of the self-sensing actuator. a) Image of bending, straining, pressure effects, and finger support on the sensing actuator. b) Images showcasing the soft robotic finger gloves in open and closed positions. c) Comparison of the resistance change ($\Delta R/R_0$) during unassisted and assisted finger bending. d) Electrical signal representation of the assisted finger bending over 7 cycles.

actuator achieves a maximum bending angle of 180° , showcasing the sensing element's responsiveness and its ability to accurately detect various bending angles. The sensor exhibits remarkable resilience in the presence of substantial bending deformation, unlike flexible sensors used in other studies that exhibit adverse effects on sensing properties due to the diverse mechanical properties of constituent materials. Figure 3d compares the bending angle characterization of the sensing and non-sensing pneumatic actuators during inlet pressure measurements ranging from 110 to 195 kPa. As the actuator is initially 2D before inflation, the bending angle is computed through image processing after reaching an internal pressure of 120 kPa. The results demonstrate that integrating the stitched sensor into the actuator has minimal impact on the maximum 180° bending angle. However, at pressure values of 150–195 kPa, the bending angle of the sensor-integrated actuator increases, potentially due to the higher pressures required to overcome the limiting influence of the sensor stitching. Figure 3e displays five complete cycles of the bending actuator, including both inflation and deflation. Throughout these cycles, the relative resistance decreases with bending motion and returns to its initial value as the bending angle decreases. Moreover, the bending angle remains constant over the actuation cycles. The actuator inflates within 7.5 s at an actuation strain rate of $8\% \text{ s}^{-1}$, while deflation takes 4.5 s to reach the maximum bending angle of 180° . The deflation cycle is faster than the inflation cycle, likely due to the opposing forces of atmospheric pressure and the recovery of the actuator's textile structure. Figure 3f illustrates the nearly linear relationship between grip force and applied pressure for the actuators. During testing, our actuator

exhibits a maximum blocking force of 3.8 N at 195 kPa, providing sufficient strength to enable bending similar to the human finger (Movie S4, Supporting Information).

2.2. Sensing Finger Glove Application

Textile actuators offer several advantages for robotic hand applications, including their softness, comfort, breathability, and wearability compared to rigid and other soft materials. These characteristics make them suitable for safe human–machine interaction, resembling human body tissues.^[46] However, for effective control and manipulation of a soft robotic hand, it is essential to incorporate a sensing mechanism that enables the hand to perceive its posture and movements.^[47]

To demonstrate the capabilities of our sensing textile actuator, we integrated the actuator onto the outer surface of a wearable finger glove, specifically designed to assist the index finger. The fabric of the glove was carefully selected to provide a secure grip, offer stretchability, avoid finger injury by preventing excessive squeezing, and maintain a lightweight design to facilitate finger flexion. The robotic glove weighs only 15 grams due to the lightweight nature of the textile material and the simplicity of the design.

The sensing mechanism of the actuator glove functions in response to bending, straining, pressure, and finger support, as depicted in Figure 4a. The actuator is securely fixed to the glove using stitching, and the sensor's response to finger flexion and relaxed motions is measured, as shown in Figure 4b. Experimental

tests were conducted to examine finger bending with and without the assistance of the actuator (Figure 4c). The results indicate that the relative resistance change generally decreases during unassisted finger bending, while increasing during assisted finger movement (Movie S4, Supporting Information). Conversely, when the finger is relaxed, the results exhibit the opposite behavior. The integration of the actuator into the glove capitalizes on the natural support provided by healthy human fingers from beneath. This support results in a counterforce applied to the actuator, thereby limiting its full actuating potential. Notably, the actuator's activation range was wider before it was integrated into the glove.

It is worth noting that the behavior of the sensor differs when the actuator is not integrated into the glove (Figure 3c) compared to when it is integrated into the human hand. As the fingers provide support to the actuator from underneath, the contact points of the sensor stitches remain in contact, and the conductive threads experience increased contact due to the pressure effect. Figure 4d illustrates the repeatability of the sensor's behavior during assisted finger-bending action over seven cycles.

The conducted experiments demonstrate that the soft finger glove is capable of sensing the bending angle at pneumatic pressure intervals ranging from 0 to 195 kPa. This showcases the effectiveness of our sensing textile actuator in enabling precise finger motion detection and control.

2.3. Modeling and Close-Loop Control of Textile Bending Robot

Using the MATLAB System Identification Toolbox, we employed the unit-step response of the sensing actuator in its non-integrated state to identify the transfer function and state space equation, as well as to assess the system's stability. The estimated transfer functions and state space functions, along with simulated response comparisons, are presented for both the inflation and deflation modes of operation. The positive signs of the denominators in the transfer functions indicate stability, as the poles are negative. These system identification and controller design studies serve the purpose of demonstrating the system's stability and providing valuable insights for future research directions.

2.3.1. Modeling of Resistance (Ω) -Pressure (kPa)

The transfer function models and simulated response comparisons, along with the fitting percentage of the acquired data and predicted model, are presented in Equations 1 and 2, respectively.

$$\left. \frac{\Delta R}{\Delta P} \right|_{\text{inflation}} = e^{-1.07s} \frac{0.003595 s + 0.01957}{s^2 + 0.474 s + 0.03196} \quad (1)$$

$$\left. \frac{\Delta R}{\Delta P} \right|_{\text{deflation}} = e^{-1.07s} \frac{1170 s^2 + 1402 s + 1407}{s^3 + 2091 s^2 + 2533 s + 1722} \quad (2)$$

As observed from the transfer functions, both inflation and deflation modes have a delay of 1.07 s. The fitting percentage of the estimated transfer function model with the acquired data is calculated as 91.01% for inflation and 97.81% for deflation, as depicted

in Figure 5a,b. The estimated state-space equations for the inflation mode are as follows:

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = -0.045 x(t) + 0.134 \times 10^{-3} u(t) + 0.184 e(t) \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma(t) = 164.7x(t) + e(t) \quad (4)$$

The estimated state-space equations for deflation mode are obtained by:

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = 0.026x(t) + 1.085 \times 10^{-5} u(t) - 0.155 e(t) \quad (5)$$

$$\gamma(t) = -194.7x(t) + e(t) \quad (6)$$

where $\gamma(t)$ represents the resistance in Ohms, $x(t)$ is a stretch state variable of the sensor, $u(t)$ is the pressure in kPa, and $e(t)$ is the disturbance. The fit between the estimated model and the experimental results is calculated as 95.18% for inflation and 78.29% for deflation. Despite the delay exceeding 1 s, the estimated model is highly suitable for periodic reference tracking applications.

2.3.2. Modeling of Resistance (Ω)-Bending Angle ($^\circ$)

The resistance-bending angle relation of the actuator is estimated and modeled for both inflation and deflation modes of operation, with a minimal delay of only 0.2 s. The transfer function and simulated response comparison are given:

$$\left. \frac{\Delta R}{\Delta \theta} \right|_{\text{inflation}} = e^{-0.2s} \frac{0.02615}{s + 0.02416} \quad (7)$$

$$\left. \frac{\Delta R}{\Delta \theta} \right|_{\text{deflation}} = e^{-0.2s} \frac{0.0113 s + 0.2011}{s^2 + 0.6322 s + 0.02416} \quad (8)$$

The estimated state-space equations for inflation mode are:

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = -0.024x(t) + 5.162 \times 10^{-5} u(t) + 0.06 e(t) \quad (9)$$

$$\gamma(t) = 506.6x(t) + e(t) \quad (10)$$

The estimated state-space equations for deflation mode are:

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = 0.0173x(t) - 2.709 \times 10^{-5} u(t) - 0.0746 e(t) \quad (11)$$

$$\gamma(t) = -440.5x(t) + e(t) \quad (12)$$

where $\gamma(t)$ represents resistance in Ohms, $x(t)$ is a stretch state variable of the sensor, $u(t)$ is the pressure in kPa, and $e(t)$ is the disturbance. The fit of the transfer function models with the acquired data is determined to be 97.26% for inflation and 99.62% for deflation of the actuator. Additionally, the fit of the state-space models with the acquired data is calculated at 95.84% for inflation and 78.05% for deflation, as depicted in Figure 5c,d, respectively. Due to the estimated computational costs of controllers in real microcontroller operations, higher-degree state-space models were not computed. Instead, transfer function models are

Figure 5. a) Inflation mode of resistance-pressure model prediction versus robot behavior. b) Deflation of resistance-pressure model prediction versus robot behavior. c) Inflation mode of resistance-bending angle model prediction versus robot behavior. d) Deflation mode of resistance-bending angle model prediction versus robot behavior.

deemed sufficient and more suitable for implementation in real microcontroller operations using the basic inverse Laplace transform and Newton–Raphson method.

2.3.3. Closed-Loop Control Simulation

To simulate the closed-loop control for the bending angle application, the provided control block diagram in **Figure 6a** is utilized. The simulation process involves system identification of the relay driver model actuator block and the air pressure and bending actuator system model plant block. Following this, the actuator and plant models are computed for further analysis and evaluation.

Inflation bending actuator model is:

$$G_p(s) = \frac{200}{8.8s + 1} \quad (13)$$

The deflation bending actuator model is:

$$G_p(s) = \frac{180}{3.7s + 1} \quad (14)$$

A phase delay and a drop in amplitude are seen when a sinusoidal input is supplied to the sensor model. This results from hysteresis between the actuator’s inner and outer kinematics. As

a result, two distinct lead compensators for the inflation and deflation phases are created. The general formula of “lead compensator” is $0 < \alpha < 1$ as follows:

$$G_f(s) = K_f \frac{s + \frac{1}{T}}{s + \frac{1}{\alpha T}} \quad (15)$$

For the inflation phase, $K_f = 3830$, $T = 41.67$, and $\alpha = 0.00024$

$$G_f(s) = K_f \frac{s + \frac{1}{T}}{s + \frac{1}{\alpha T}} = 38.3 \frac{s + 0.024}{0.01s + 1} \quad (16)$$

compensator model is used. Since the deflation phase sensor dynamics degree is higher, a higher-order compensator design is done as follows:

$$G_f(s) = 4.34 \frac{s^2 + 0.77s + 0.1}{0.01s^2 + 0.1s + 1} \quad (17)$$

The lead compensator is designed for our operating frequency between 0–16 Hz (0–100 rad s⁻¹). The lead compensator will not amplify the noises when the sensor is used, as the noises

Figure 6. a) Schematic control block diagram ($G_c(s)$, $G_p(s)$, $G_s(s)$, $G_f(s)$). b) Comparison of the sinusoid response of the sensor with and without compensator. c) Bode diagrams with and without compensator. d) Bending angle control simulation result.

Table 1. Comparison of PID controller variants.

Phase	K_p	K_i	K_d
Inflation	0.1	0.03	0.03
Deflation	0.038	0.006	0.012

generated will be at higher frequencies. **Table 1** shows the designed PID closed-loop controllers for inflation and deflation phases, where K_p , K_i , and K_d are controller parameters.

The sinusoidal response of the system with a controller is presented in Figure 6b, demonstrating the effect of the lead compensator on the output signal. The Bode diagrams in Figure 6c

provide insights into the frequency range of the designed controller, indicating its suitability for the applied reference signals. It is worth noting that the ON-OFF and tuned PID controllers produce identical control signals. The simulation results of the bending angle control model (Figure 6d) align well with the experimental data. In the simulation, a reference pressure of 114 kPa is used for the inflating mode, while a reference pressure of 0 kPa is applied for the deflation mode. Two separate controllers are designed for the sensor, considering its different transfer functions when used as a pressure sensor and a bending angle sensor. The controller's performance is evaluated against selected references with close amplitudes (60 kPa and 100°) during a simulation period of 11 s, resembling the experimental conditions for data collection.

3. Conclusion

This study has successfully demonstrated the integration of a textile-based resistive sensor into a fabric actuator, showcasing its design, fabrication, characterization, modeling, and control. By utilizing standard sewing technology, we have achieved combined sensing and mechanical capabilities without the need for extensive training or costly investments. This approach streamlines the manufacturing process, eliminating the need for additional processing in both sensor and actuator production.

Experimental evaluations have revealed remarkable performance, with the actuator achieving bending angles of up to 180° at pressures of 195 kPa, generating a maximum blocking force of 3.8 N. Notably, the stitched sensor exhibited no adverse effects on the actuator's straining ability, ensuring its reliable functionality. The developed transfer function models have proven highly effective in estimating both pressure (91.01% for inflation and 97.81% for deflation) and bending angle (97.26% for inflation and 99.62% for deflation) of the sensing actuator.

In the performance analysis of different controller variants, the simplicity of the ON–OFF controller emerged as the preferred choice. This finding emphasizes the feasibility and practicality of our approach in developing closed-loop control systems for soft robotics. Moving forward, our research will focus on refining the modeling, calibration, and control of the actuator specifically on the human hand, as the sensor's behavior may vary within the finger glove assembly.

Furthermore, we envision further advancements of this sensing actuator in applications such as grasping, assistive robotic wearables, and human rehabilitation. These promising avenues will be explored to unlock the full potential of our technology. We believe that our study will inspire fellow robotics researchers to embark on the development of simple yet highly effective sensing solutions for soft robot technologies. By sharing our findings, we aim to foster innovation and drive progress in the field of soft robotics.

4. Experimental Section

Starching Process: The corn starch (15 grams) and cold water (300 mL) were mixed until the clumps were gone. The resulting starch solution was then heated until it thickened to the desired consistency. After allowing the starch solution to cool down, a rib-knit fabric was immersed in the solution, ensuring it was fully coated. The fabric was carefully removed from the solution and left to dry on a flat surface.

Fabrication of Stitched Sensor and Textile-Based Actuator: The 1 × 1 rib knit fabric, with a thickness of 0.3 mm and dimensions of 2 cm × 13 cm, was cut using a laser cutting machine (VLS 2.30, Universal Laser Systems, Scottsdale, AZ, USA). The sensor and actuator components were then created using a sewing machine (Brother CS-6000i, Brother International, Nagoya, Japan). The actuator and sensing capability were built using commercially available rib knit fabric (65% lycra, 35% polyamides), a commercial silver-plated nylon conductive yarn (Shieldex 235 f/36 dtex 2-ply HC+B), and sewing thread (100% polyester Nm 60/2). The linear resistance of this conductive yarn was 100 Ω m⁻¹, the elasticity was up to 17 500 m kg⁻¹, the tensile strength was 46 cN tex⁻¹, and the stretching was up to 15%. The sensor was created on knit fabric using 304 zigzag stitch geometry, with the conductive thread in the bobbin thread area, and polyester stitch thread in the needle thread area of the sewing machine. 301 lockstitch, polyester thread in the bobbin, and needle threads were used to make bending anisotropy stitches. The seam that was superim-

posed was created for stitching the actuator. The air bladder was then inserted into the actuator.

Fabrication of Thermoplastic Air Bladder: An impulse sealer machine (PCS 300, Brother, Nagoya, Japan), thermoplastic polyurethane film (Stretchlon 200, Fiber Glast, Brookville, OH, USA), and polyurethane tube were used to make the air bladder. Two rectangular cut films 2 cm × 14 cm were layered on top of one another, and an impulse sealer was used to create a bond between them at a time setting of 5.5 s. The welding process was finished when all three edges of the TPU sheet with the rectangle cut-off were closed. A polyurethane tube was inserted into the open end, and a pneumatic system was used to inflate it.

Characterization of Mechanical Properties of Fabric: The mechanical characteristics of knit fabric were tested at a speed of 100 mm min⁻¹ using a commercial uniaxial testing machine (Titan 5, James Heal, UK) following the EN ISO 13934-1 test standard. Five 20 cm × 5 cm pieces of knit fabric were cut in the course-wale directions. The fabric was treated for 24 h in a typical atmospheric environment before the test. Data for both the extension (mm) and force (N) were recorded. Using the mean of five samples, a force-extension graph was made to identify the direction of greater fabric extension.

Electromechanical Characterization of the Strain Sensor: The electromechanical properties of the stitched-strain sensor were evaluated using a vertical tensile tester (ESM 303, Mark-10, Copiague, NY, USA). This testing apparatus allowed for precise measurements of the response of the sensor to mechanical strain, providing valuable data on its performance under various conditions. For each strain experiment, strain velocity was adjusted at 1000 mm min⁻¹. The resistance value of the actuator was measured using Keysight 34465A Digital Multimeter. Strain and resistance values were collected and synchronized by a computer. The resistive strain sensor works by measuring relative changes in:

$$R = \rho \frac{L}{A} \quad (18)$$

where R is the electrical resistivity of the conductive yarn, the resistivity ρ of the conductive material, L is the length of the strain sensor, and A is its cross-sectional area. Experiments were conducted in normal atmospheric conditions.

Actuation: An air pump, valve, relay, pressure sensor, and microcontroller were all parts of the airflow system. An air pump motor (DC 12 V/370-02PM-SKU-5000, Makeblock, Shenzhen, China) was used to actuate the textile actuator. The air pump and solenoid valve (12 V 2W-025-08, Senya) were controlled by the 5 V 4 channel relay board and Arduino Nano microcontroller. Using an air pressure sensor (MPXHZ6250A, Freescale Semiconductor, USA), the actuator's internal pressure was measured.

Characterization of Sensing Actuator: The sensing actuator was fastened and coupled to a pneumatic-valve control system that included a pressurized air supply and a pressure sensor. The input pressure was adjusted between 0 and 195 kPa to evaluate the connection between air pressure and normalized peak electrical resistance during actuation. As with strain sensor characterization, the electrical resistance was measured using a digital multimeter (34465A, Keysight, California, USA) connected to two ends of the resistive sensor. To eliminate any sort of undesired motion, the probes were fixated on the test setup. The extracted resistance values and corresponding timestamp data were transmitted to, recorded, and observed on the computer in a real-time manner. To better investigate the change in resistance of the actuator concerning its bending behavior, the resistance, and bending angle values were recorded while the actuator was pressurized and depressurized six consecutive times. Out of the six pressurization and depressurization cycles, the first one was eliminated in all of the conducted experiments to obtain stable results by avoiding the possible dislocations of the actuator in the initial cycle. While conducting the experiments, one end of the actuator was fixated on a custom-made test rig, while the other end followed a circular motion without any restraint to overcome the aforementioned undesired dislocation problem. Also, the pressure range in each cycle was kept constant that is the minimum and maximum pressure capacity of the actuator to have comparable results.

While the actuator was inflated and deflated by the control system,^[40] the bending motion was recorded via a camera located on the plane of the actuator. Both the actuator and the camera were placed in a secluded area to achieve stable lighting conditions. By implementing several image processing techniques such as contouring on the three color markers attached to the extreme points of the actuator, the markers' center of mass coordinates were calculated. The bending angle value was then computed according to these coordinates. In the experiments, the locations of the extreme points were set to mimic the knuckles of a finger. At each frame of the captured video of the actuator's motion, the bending angle value and its corresponding timestamp were obtained. Since the amount of data obtained per second from the multimeter and the number of extracted bending angle values from frames of the captured video per second were different, these values were then matched up according to their timestamps in such a way that the resistance values were coupled with the bending angle value with the closest timestamp. The resistance values were represented as the change in the resistance concerning the initial resistance value. The mean bending angle value through all cycles corresponding to the same resistance value was calculated. The same method was utilized for matching the pressure data obtained from the control system with the bending angle results. Here, the mean and the range of the pressure data were calculated for each corresponding bending angle value.

To analyze the gripping capability of the soft sensing bending actuator, using the grip force test setup established in the previous work,^[48] the exerted grip force according to the applied pressure was recorded by utilizing a digital dynamometer (SH-50, Geratech, Istanbul, Turkey).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

bioinspired soft robotics, resistive strain sensors, self-sensing actuators, sensors, soft actuators, soft robotics, textile-based actuators

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